

DESIGN OF COMPETITIVE LIGHT-WEIGHT COMPOSITE MATERIALS: SiC/TiSi₂

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1. Introduction

Light, stiff and strong materials capable of bearing load have become increasingly valuable for the design, construction and assembling of lightweight transportation systems such as aircraft, high-speed trains or even for the construction of satellites. In spite of the need, there are few promising new materials in current development that are suited for advanced applications. It is not surprising that R&D is highly focused on advanced ceramics and composites, i.e. MMC-type where the metal phase is an Al, Si or Ti-based alloy. To produce SiC-based composites with desirable properties, the reactive infiltration process has well known advantages over other conventional processing techniques. These processing routes have particular advantages over classical sintering and hot-pressing techniques, i.e. lower processing temperatures, shorter times and near-net shape fabrication capabilities. However, many aspects are still not fully understood mainly related to the interfacial phenomena occurring during infiltration process. Currently, three are the greatest open challenges for scientists: theoretical description of the process by computational models, decrease or replacement of the unreacted Si, and finally, the possibility to “control” the “pore closure” phenomenon. A key contribution could be coming from know-how on wetting characteristics, reactivity, surface properties and thermodynamics concerning reacting phases [1].

Systematic investigations of wetting characteristics, reactivity, surface properties and thermodynamics concerning Si-Ti/C-based substrate couple have been carried out. In addition, infiltration experiments have been performed between Si-Ti/C-preform with different porosity. All the collected findings will be detailed in a next paper. In this work, the more relevant results obtained by wetting tests will be reported and briefly discussed.

2. Materials and Methods

For wetting tests, pure Si, as reference element, and three different Si-Ti alloy compositions have been selected: TiSi₂ intermetallic compound, Si-16at%Ti eutectic composition and Si-8at%Ti hypereutectic

alloy. The alloys have been produced by mixing high pure Si and Ti (99.998% GoodFellow©) and melted by arc-melting. Each as-produced alloy composition has been checked by SEM/EDS analyses.

As substrates, glassy-C (GC-provided by Alfa Aesar©) and Hot Pressed-SiC (HP-SiC-provided by GoodFellow©) have been chosen. Prior the experiments, the surface of each substrate has been characterized by 3D-profilometer showing a roughness around 20nm and 1µm for GC and HP-SiC, respectively.

Wettability, spreading kinetics, reactivity, surface and bulk properties (surface tension and density) as a function of composition and operative conditions (time, temperature, total pressure), have been estimated by sessile/pendant drop combined method [2] in the temperature range of (T_m+20)-1550°C (Figure 1). In particular, wetting behaviour and spreading kinetics have been compared with the results obtained by contact heating sessile drop method [1].

Fig.1. Surface tension and wetting combined experiments: Si-Ti alloy pendant drop for surface tension measurements combined with dispensed Si-Ti alloy onto GC and HP-SiC for wettability tests.

Moreover, dynamic of infiltration has been evaluated by combining contact heating and dispensed drop methods, as a function of operating conditions, i.e. temperature, average porous radius, C-content in the preform.

Interfacial phenomena and resulting microstructure have been carefully analyzed in terms of thickness and composition of the reaction layer, by OM, SEM-EDS and 3D-Tomography techniques. In parallel, surface and bulk properties outcomes have been compared with the predicted values obtained by applying Ideal

solution, Quasi-Chemical Approximation (QCA) for regular solution models applied at the base of Si-Ti system as done in [3].

A preliminary thermodynamic study of Si-Ti-C system has been also performed.

3. Results and discussion

In Figure 2, the evolution of wetting behavior of Si-16%Ti eutectics/GC couple within a contact heating experiment (heating rate $\approx 10^\circ/\text{sec}$) performed at $T = 1350^\circ\text{C}$, is shown. Spreading kinetics is also reported in terms of drop radius as a function of time.

Fig. 2. Contact angle and base drop radius as a function of time of Si-16%Ti/GC couple at $T = 1350^\circ\text{C}$.

As it can be seen, four different spreading stages have been observed. In particular, the stage ($t_0 \div t_1$) is typical of wetting experiments performed close to the melting point (T_m Si-16Ti = 1330°C [4]) by contact heating sessile drop method. The presence of SiO_2 -primary oxide at the surface affects in delaying the melting of the drop. Moreover, the oxide skin initially prevents the intimate contact between the melt and the substrate. In the second spreading stage ($t_1 \div t_2$), the change of the dR/dT , reveals that silicon is dissolving the SiO_2 wetting barrier. As a consequence, the Si-Ti melt is prompt to react with C, to form SiC as a reaction product [5]. The linear spreading behaviour observed in this stage suggests that Si-16%Ti/C wetting behaviour is purely governed by the reaction at the triple line, named “linear” reactive wetting by [6]. Within the third stage of spreading ($t_2 \div t_3$) a linear dependency is also observed. At the Si-16%Ti/C couple, “linear” reactive wetting is still the dominant mechanism. The decrease of the slope suggests that a “competitive” phenomenon

is in progress.

Fig. 3. SEM Image at the triple of the solidified Si-16%Ti/GC couple after wetting test performed at $T = 1350^\circ\text{C}$.

As evidenced by SEM/EDS analyses (Figure 3), two are the possible competitors for advancing contact

angle: the change of the substrate roughness given by the growth/packaging of SiC crystals [7] at Si-16%Ti/GC interface and evaporation/condensation phenomena close to the triple line.

4. Summary and conclusions

Combined theoretical-experimental approach has been applied to fully investigate the interfacial phenomena occurring at Si-Ti/C-based interfaces.

All the interaction phenomena are strongly dependent on the temperature, as expected. In addition, competitive phenomena, i.e. evaporation/condensation of Si at the triple line, combined with the epitaxial growth/packaging of SiC crystals at Si-Ti/C interfaces, strongly affect the spreading kinetics. Moreover, the advancing contact angle is also influenced by the procedure applied: the presence SiO_2 -primary oxide at the alloy surface processed by contact heating sessile drop method, inhibits or delays the first appearance of Si-Ti/C interface. On the contrary, the presence of this oxide skin, mitigates the Si-evaporation, at least at $T \approx T_m$.

In view to relate these evidences with reactive infiltration processes, such knowledge may be helpful to select the optimal operating parameters to obtain tailored SiC-TiSi₂ composites.

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